

1 Title: A Rare Case of Pediatric Death from Systemic Loxoscelism

2 Short Title: Pediatric Death from Loxoscelism

3 Author(s): Benjamin T. Hinkle, MD, Clinical Assistant Professor of Family Medicine, UAB-

4 Huntsville Regional Medical Center

5 Contact Information: dr.tatemd@gmail.com; 706-590-5550; 944 Andrews Ave, Auburn, AL

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24 Abstract

25 Systemic loxoscelism is a rare condition that results in systemic effects after envenomation from
26 *Loxosceles reclusa* (brown recluse spider). A 5 year old boy presented to the pediatric
27 emergency room on transfer from an outside hospital after envenomation from a known brown
28 recluse spider. He quickly developed systemic effects including signs and symptoms of
29 hemolysis, respiratory distress, and dermatologic manifestations. He rapidly deteriorated over
30 approximately 5 hours at our hospital and subsequently passed away approximately 15.5 hours
31 after envenomation. In this case study, a rare case of death from systemic loxoscelism in a
32 pediatric patient is described to raise awareness of its possibility. Brown recluse spider bites are
33 not uncommon but systemic loxoscelism and death resulting from it are very rare. Due to the
34 widespread nature of brown recluse bites, awareness of the potential complications resulting
35 from envenomation is an important clinical consideration.

36 Keywords: brown recluse, spider bite

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47 Introduction

48 Loxoscelism is a condition that is the result of envenomation from the bite of the genus
49 *Loxosceles*, most commonly in the United States it is from *Loxosceles reclusa* (brown recluse
50 spider) [1]. The effects can range from dermatologic manifestations and local site reactions to
51 systemic effects such as disseminated intravascular coagulopathy, renal failure, multisystem
52 organ failure and rarely death [1-3]. We describe a unique case of death from systemic
53 loxoscelism in a pediatric patient in less than 24 hours after envenomation.

54 Case Report

55 A previously healthy 5-year-old boy presented for evaluation after a known spider bite.
56 Around 9:00am, the boy felt something under his shirt and felt a sudden sting and swatted
57 around his right shoulder blade where he felt the sting. A brown spider fell out of his shirt and
58 his mother having been bitten by a brown recluse spider several years ago recognized the spider
59 as a brown recluse. The patient was taken to a local urgent care center for evaluation where he
60 was afebrile but was showing early signs of a systemic response to the bite, thus he was sent to
61 the local emergency department. At the local emergency department he was given a 400 cc bolus
62 of normal saline, 20mg of famotidine, 12.5mg of diphenhydramine, 4mg of dexamethasone, 1
63 gram of ceftriaxone, and 480mg of acetaminophen. His laboratory studies at the local emergency
64 department showed a mildly elevated creatine phosphokinase (CPK) level at 332 IU/L, an
65 elevated c-reactive protein at 4 mg/mL, an elevated total bilirubin at 1.6 mg/dL. Additionally, his
66 hemoglobin was 11.8 g/dL and his hematocrit was 36.8%. He was transferred to our Urban
67 Pediatric Emergency Department for further evaluation and management.

68 On arrival to our ED, his vital signs were temperature 37.7°C (99.8°F), heart rate 99,
69 blood pressure 102/82 mmHg, respiratory rate 20, oxygen saturation 100% on room air. His

70 initial physical exam showed a mildly ill appearing, but alert, attentive and in no acute distress.
71 His HEENT, neck, lungs, heart, abdominal and neurological exam were all normal; the exam
72 was notable for puncture wound in the posterior right scapular area that was surrounded by an
73 8cm x 10cm area of edema and induration. The mother reported that the size of the area of
74 edema and induration was significantly larger than it had been this morning.

75 Initial laboratory studies, that were drawn at approximately 6:35pm, showed an elevated
76 c-reactive protein (CRP) at 1.0 mg/mL, complete blood count showed an elevated WBC count at
77 16,520/ μ L (normal range 5000-15,500) , hemoglobin of 10.2 g/dL (normal range 11.5-13.5),
78 hematocrit of 30.8% (normal range 33.0-40.0). His coagulation studies showed an elevated
79 Protime of 15.6 seconds with an elevated INR of 1.3. A liver function panel was drawn with the
80 initial lab work, which showed an elevated direct bilirubin at 0.5 mg/dL, however the total
81 bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase, alanine aminotransferase, and aspartate aminotransferase were
82 not able to be determined due to the level of hemolysis of the blood sample.

83 A CPK level was also drawn initially and not able to be calculated due to hemolysis. The
84 CPK and liver function panel were subsequently redrawn at approximately 8:00pm and 10:40pm
85 but both additional samples could not be evaluated due to the level of hemolysis.

86 His emergency room course deteriorated throughout his stay in our emergency
87 department. He had an oxygen desaturation to 88% on room air at approximately 7:40pm while
88 sleeping and was started on 3L of oxygen by nasal cannula. At approximately 8:30pm, the
89 pediatric hospitalist service was consulted to admit the patient to the hospital and they requested
90 that the emergency room physician obtain the liver function panel before sending the patient to
91 the floor. His condition continued to deteriorate after acceptance by the floor team where a
92 recheck of his vital signs at approximately 9:00pm showed he has now become febrile with a

93 temperature of 38.6°C (101.4°F), heart rate of 121, respiratory rate of 20, and oxygen saturation
94 of 96% on 3L of oxygen by nasal cannula. At approximately 9:30pm his laboratory work was
95 redrawn to attempt to measure the CPK level and liver function panel but they were again unable
96 to be measured due to hemolysis. Additionally, his reevaluation showed a worsening of the area
97 surrounding the puncture wound. It had begun to spread to his axillary area, had begun turning
98 purple in color, and the size had grown to 9cm x 12cm.

99 The floor team resident was called down to the ER to further evaluate the patient at 9:20
100 PM and upon arrival the patient was vomiting. Per report of the ED physician and ED nurse, the
101 patient had not urinated since arriving at the emergency room. At that time a bladder scan
102 revealed very little urine in the bladder (41 cc) despite 710 cc of fluid being given both at the
103 outside hospital and our facility. A recheck of the patient's hemoglobin and hematocrit at that
104 time showed a marked decrease to 7.6 g/dL and 22% from the previous of 10.2 g/dL and 30.8%
105 at our facility over 2 hours. With the patient continuing to deteriorate, the floor team and the ED
106 physician agreed the patient needed closer monitoring and consulted the pediatric intensivist to
107 evaluate and admit the patient to the pediatric intensive care unit (PICU).

108 The pediatric intensivist presented to the ED to evaluate the patient and accepted him to
109 their service at approximately 10:00pm. At 10:15pm, a third liver panel and CPK level was
110 hemolyzed. At 10:45pm the patient was taken up to the PICU. On admission to the PICU the
111 patient did look moderately ill but was awake, alert and oriented and was talking with staff and
112 the pediatric intensivist. After the initial exam and assessment, the pediatric intensivist left the
113 bedside to get further history from the patient's family. At 11:10pm, the pediatric intensivist was
114 emergently called back to the PICU as the patient had developed premature ventricular
115 contractions (PVCs) and one minute of ventricular fibrillation and the resuscitation began.

116 Throughout the resuscitation the patient received a total of 19 shocks, 5 doses of epinephrine, 7
117 doses of sodium bicarbonate, 4 doses of calcium chloride, 3 doses of atropine, 2 doses of
118 amiodarone followed by a bolus, among several other PALS drugs. Despite the medications
119 being maxed out he could not maintain an adequate rhythm or an adequate perfusing pressure.
120 He was ventilated and intubated throughout the resuscitation with good oxygen saturations but
121 his lactic acid levels during the resuscitation were 20 mmol/L and 18 mmol/L (normal range <2.0
122 mmol/L). Unfortunately, after 41 minutes of resuscitative efforts the patient was pronounced
123 dead at 12:21am, approximately 15.5 hours after envenomation.

124 Discussion

125 While brown recluse bites are not uncommon, death from a brown recluse bite in this
126 manner and in such a rapid fashion is exceedingly rare with a literature review only finding one
127 additional case reported in the literature [4]. There are many potential serious systemic
128 complications from systemic loxoscelism from brown recluse spider envenomation including
129 multiorgan failure, hematologic manifestations including hemolytic anemia and disseminated
130 intravascular coagulopathy, and dermatologic manifestations including necrosis of the wound.
131 Often times, children are more at risk for serious complications from brown recluse
132 envenomation and specifically are more likely to exhibit hematologic manifestations [3,5]. The
133 standard of care for systemic loxoscelism remains supportive including hemodynamic support
134 and blood product transfusion targeted at laboratory supported deficiencies remains crucial in
135 determining outcomes especially when identified and treated early in the course of systemic
136 loxoscelism [1,3]. There have been other proposed treatments such as dapsone, steroids, and
137 other broad-spectrum antibiotics but none of these treatments have been shown to provide a
138 mortality benefit in systemic loxoscelism [4]. Due to the potential for serious complications from

139 brown recluse spider envenomation, it is imperative that providers are aware of the possible
140 complications to be able to adequately diagnose and treat these complications.

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